

SEMANTIC AND STYLISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LITOTES

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Abstract. This article discusses the semantic and stylistic features of litota. It is also one of the important factors in world linguistics that the study of a particular language on the basis of its specific national, historical features, litota is often used in fiction, poetry to enhance the descriptive and expressive features of speech, both in prose and poetry. both figurative, euphonic speech, and emphasis on key concepts have been explored.

Key words: linguistics, litota, semantics, literary text, poetry, speech, imagery, expressiveness, stylistics, hyperbole, exaggeration, simplicity, phenomenon.

СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ И СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ЛИТОТЫ

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются смысловые и стилистические особенности литоты. Также одним из важных факторов мировой лингвистики является то, что изучение того или иного языка на основе его специфических национальных, исторических особенностей, литота часто используется в художественной литературе, поэзии для усиления описательных и выразительных характеристик речи, как в прозе. были исследованы как образная, благозвучная речь, так и акцент на ключевых концепциях.

Ключевые слова: лингвистика, литота, семантика, художественный текст, поэзия, речь, образность, выразительность, стилистика, гипербола, преувеличение, простота, феномен.

Introduction.

In recent times, world linguistics has paid special attention not only to the structure of language, but also to the study of the internal form of words in the language, semantics.

Anthropocentric paradigm, cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology are developing rapidly, and the trends in the complex study of literary texts are improving. During the years of independence, the revival of our national values has led to the development of our native language, which reflects the spiritual world of our people, and the further expansion of its use in society. In particular, one of the urgent tasks is to study in depth and comprehensively our native language, which is "the symbol of our national identity and independent statehood, invaluable spiritual wealth, great values ... a solid foundation of the nation's spirituality." In world linguistics, the main focus is not only on the semantics of the word, but also on the relationship between the word and the speech of a particular subject, its pragmatic content, evaluative attitude, national-cultural aspects.

Thanks to independence, Uzbek linguistics has reached a stage of rapid development, the importance of national and cultural factors has made it a priority to increase the volume of research in various fields of science. The need to understand our national identity, to study the ancient and rich history of our country, to strengthen scientific research in this area, to fully support the work of scientists in the humanities implies the practical results of any theoretical research.

The study of the essence of language provides an opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of the spiritual heritage, rich history, national values, cultural and spiritual riches of any nation. Litotes is often used in fiction, poetry to enhance the descriptive and expressive features of speech, and in both prose and poetry it is used for figurative, euphonic speech, and emphasizes basic concepts. Litotes serves to downplay the size or importance of someone or something in the literature.

Literature review. The custom of using litotes dates back to ancient times. Classical examples of the technique are found in “The Illiad” poem by the ancient Greek poet Homer, in which Zeus describes Achilles as saying, "He is not foolish and invisible," meaning that he is both wise and intelligent. Early literary litotes types of ancient Rome are found in Ovid's poem *Metamorphoses* (1st century): "not once," which means "more than once." Some common words are removed from the litotes: “none” is taken as “several”, “not always” - “sometimes”. The first mention of the word “litotes” is given in a letter from Cicero, an ancient Roman philosopher who used the phrase for the simplicity of life. Over time, the meaning of the word has evolved into a lower-level idea that embraces the principle of hesitation over “simplicity”. Biblical phrases are also based on litotes, for example: “My word ... is not repeated in vain” (Isaiah 55:11), meaning that the word is meaningful and meaningful. Litotes is used in both prose and poetry for expressiveness, imagery, euphonic speech, and emphasizes basic concepts. Types of denial in the literature - discrimination or mitigation - are determined by context, in speech - by intonation and emphasis. For example, depending on pronunciation or context, the word “not bad” can mean ways to both soften and soften. The term of litotes was used by the great Russian masters of words A.S.Pushkin, N.V.Gogol, A.S.Griboyedov, N.A.Nekrasov and others.

Research Methodology. Litotes (simplicity), tafrit is a method of miniature depiction in fiction. Litotes is a figurative expression, a stylistic form, a twist, which includes the size of the object or event depicted in it, the artistic reduction of its value. Litotes is the inverse of a hyperbole in this sense, so it is otherwise called an inverse hyperbole. In litotes, two different phenomena are compared on the basis of some common feature, but this feature is manifested in the means of comparison phenomena to a lesser extent than in the object of comparison and recommends the best and most appropriate means of style speech, as a rule. Defines the means used in different stylistic layers of speech.

Accordingly, methodology is a separate discipline of the art of expression. It is the linguist who enriches our understanding of this science the services of our scholars and writers are invaluable. Thanks to their hard work, strict norms have been established in many areas of the Uzbek language, and linguistic examples of language units in the communication process have been recommended. Many issues in language development are based on science. For example: Initially, in the Uzbek language, little attention was paid to the issues of visual aids and migration. It later became one of these areas. A number of works have been written in this field in linguistics and literature.

Analysis and results. Litotes is an artistic concept. This method is used when they want to discredit the actual dimensions of the object or event under consideration. When a word that confirms a particular feature of litotes is replaced by a word that denies that feature, the expression can be called a methodological cycle of special softening.

Litotes is used in the literature to downplay the size or importance of someone or something, the opposite of the hyperbole used to enhance the visual-expressive features of speech, a rare artistic example. Verbal structure of litotes comparison, metaphor, epithet. Litotes is often used in prose and poetry to describe events or characters in a work of art more accurately and colorfully. In the richest Russian language there are many speech twists, phrases that allow to give any dictum the desired emotional color, to make it more or less bright. Among these conditions, litotes occupies one of the last places. It is an intentional artistic discrimination that can be applied to a person or object, to the characteristics of a particular event or phenomenon. As a rule, such a distortion of speech is avoided if the narrator doubts that this action has been fully performed, or if the person has this or that feature in maturity.

The litotes in Russian is an understatement, which in turn is an exaggeration for the properties of an object or some human ability. The path we are considering is formed by applying a two-sided negation in speech if it is to show the negative side of any one, for example, not without reason. If, on the contrary, it is necessary to emphasize dignity, but not much to praise, then the litotic path is formed using negatively colored words, for example: not bad, without heat, and so on. Often in literature and everyday speech, such deviations are used to turn the rejection of something into morality. An example of this is: "You're not sure you can do the task." What this means is that the speaker is convinced: the interlocutor cannot perform the task.

However, with the help of rejection, he absolutely reflected this. In this case, litotes is a softening used in speech not to openly express your dissatisfaction, but to do it gently. This misguided and rejected approach is often found in fiction, as well as in articles of a cognitive nature. They make the text more colorful, interesting, and often force the reader to return to the lines read to fully understand their meaning. Litotes are also used during communication during operation. Often, deliberate discrimination is used in speech to politely point out possible mistakes to a boss or a senior employee. Hearing this, any person involuntarily thinks about the correctness of their actions. If you tell him openly about the mistake, the dispute will start.

Litotes is also a very common style in fairy tales and folk art. Here, misjudgment is achieved not by rejecting an object or event, but by identifying it with a tiny, tiny thing. Litotes improves the meaning of words and phrases as a way of discrimination, focusing on specific events by reducing their signs. In this sense, litotes is opposed to hyperbola, which is why it is also called "reverse hyperbola". Litotes is often used for ethical reasons: humility and lowering one's achievements allow one to form a positive opinion about it.

For example, an experienced driver uses the phrase "This is not my first trip" to gain the confidence of passengers in assessing their professional skills. Stylistics, a relatively new branch of Uzbek linguistics, deals with the use of linguistic units as a means of communication in various fields and situations, the laws of speech organization, the possibilities of all means in the language system in the speech process and the subtleties of meaning. "Stylistics recommends all the tools available in a language, how to use lexical, grammatical, phonetic tools in speech, which of a certain type of form, word and construction is appropriate, the best and most appropriate tool.

Defines as a norm, the means used in different stylistic layers of speech. Therefore, stylistics is the study of the art of expression."

The main task of linguistics is to clearly define language units based on knowledge of language, taking into account changes in their mutual syntagmatic, paradigmatic, form-content and other relations (origin, period, region) and their application in speech. It should be about disclosing opportunities. The main task of the methodology is to determine the normality of the possibilities of language units in relation to the laws of manifestation in speech, period, appearance of speech. All research in linguistics and stylistics must be focused on these tasks. This certainly does not negate the other tasks that arise from the relationship of both linguistics and stylistics to other fields. Knowing many writers, being able to read texts, being able to write in many writings, knowing many languages, being able to speak these languages are some of the best qualities of human beings. The level of human perfection is first of all reflected in his speech.

Conclusion. Language is the heart of a nation and it is a changing, ever-moving phenomenon. Language change is seen as a pragmatic opportunity in the process of speech, in use.

Language, no matter how big or small, is a stronghold of any nation. National identity is expressed in more languages. After the independence of our country, the development of language and linguistics has become very important. A review of the history of the development of world linguistics, the development of the most valuable linguistic traditions in it, is associated with certain reasons.

- ✚ the linguistic relationship to linguistic achievements has been abolished;
- ✚ a social approach to structuralism and its manifestations has emerged;
- ✚ it has been practically proved that in order to study many unresolved problems of modern linguistics, it is necessary to critically examine the achievements of linguistics of the past;

The history of linguistics shows that the development of linguistic theories is largely consistent with the development of the most important philosophical currents from antiquity to the present day. It is no coincidence that in the process of globalization, opinions are expressed about the prospects of national languages, their status in society, their prestige. Because language as a social phenomenon plays an important role in people's activities in various fields. Our centuries-old history shows that the role of enlightenment, especially the social sciences, in the formation of the human worldview is invaluable. Whether it's linguistics, history, philosophy, political science, psychology or economics in a society, they all have a huge impact on a person's intellectual maturity.

REFERENCES

1. Abdurahmonov X., Mahmudov N. Word aesthetics. –Tashkent: Fan, 1981.
2. Abdullaev A. Expression of expressiveness in Uzbek language. –Tashkent: Fan, 1983.- 88-p.
3. Kungurov R. Visual aids of the Uzbek language. –Tashkent: Fan, 1977.
4. Boboev T., Boboeva Z. Fine arts. –Tashkent: TDPI, 2001.
5. Doniyorov X., Mirzaev S. Word art (artistic skills and language considerations). – Tashkent: Fan: 1962.
6. Jamolkhonov H., Yuldashev M. Linguistic analysis of the literary text (Text of lectures). – Tashkent: TDPU, 2000.
7. Karimov S.A. Problems of Uzbek language methodology at the present stage. Text of lectures. - Samarkand, 2006.

8. Karimov S.A. Functional stylistics of the Uzbek language. - Samarkand, 2010. [9] Bekiyeva M. "Linguculturological research directions and interpretation of language and culture in modern linguistics". Electronic journal of actual problems of modern science, education and training. 2020. 106-117 p
9. Shomaksudov A., Rasulov I., Kungurov R., Rustamov H. Stylistics of the Uzbek language. -Tashkent: Teacher, 1983.-247 p.
10. Mukarramov M. Classification of similarities // Uzbek language and literature, T.: 1968
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